

Risk-Aware Motion Planning for Autonomous Mobile Robots Navigation

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Abstract—This paper proposes a method to deal with collision risk during robot navigation in a quantitative way. Risk is intended not simply as collision probability, as usually done in motion planning literature, but as a combination of probability and severity. First, a collision probability map is computed using lidars measurements. Then, a modified Anytime Weighted A* adjusts in real-time a reference trajectory to compute the minimum-risk path considering both collision probability and severity. If the collision probability part of the risk is too high and the planner cannot find a safe path (i.e., with a risk below a desired threshold), an active sensing module is activated for reducing the uncertainty about the map. The proposed framework is also suitable for the introduction of new risk factors such as battery discharge and friction coefficient. The system has been tested on a Robotnik summit-xl-steel in Gazebo.

Index Terms—risk-aware motion planning, mobile robots, navigation

I. INTRODUCTION

When an autonomous mobile robot operates in a dynamic environment, it encounters several potential hazards such as obstacles, humans, and other moving robots. These risks can lead to undesirable interactions, damage to delicate objects, harm to the robot, and even endanger human safety. Therefore, it is crucial to acknowledge and explicitly address these different risk factors when operating the robot. To ensure successful mission completion in real-world settings, it is essential to provide autonomous agents with a heightened awareness of uncertainty and the possibility of failure.

In the context of risk management, risk is defined as an uncertain event that, if it occurs, negatively affects the success of a task. Risk is evaluated based on the combination of probability and severity [1]. Risk probability, also known as likelihood, refers to the chance of a risk event happening, while risk consequence, also known as severity or impact, represents the outcome resulting from the occurrence of the risk event.

However, in robotics, risk is usually understood simply as the probability of collision. In the state of the art, there are several works with the aim of quantifying and minimizing the probability of collision along the robot trajectory [8], [2].

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Other works investigate the severity of possible collisions and identify a maximum speed value at which the robot should move, regardless of the distance from humans [6].

The ISO/TS 15066 [3], which regulates collaborative operations, prescribes two different methods to assure safety when an autonomous robot moves in a workspace shared with humans: Speed Separation Monitoring (SSM), and Power Force Limiting (PFL). SSM and PFL are considered by the normative as alternative methods. SSM depends on the estimation of the relative distance and velocity, as well as the current needed breaking time and measurement uncertainty in that particular environmental conditions and robot configuration. SSM prevents the collision from happening. PFL, instead, does not guarantee the absence of collisions, but imposes maximum energy transferred during the impact, so, we can see it as a way to reduce the severity part of the collision risk.

In this work, we will present a planner that reasons risk minimization intending risk as a combination of probability and severity, according to the risk management definition.

II. METHOD

We consider a mobile omnidirectional robot equipped with two 2D lidars and encoders, which operate in a dynamic environment. The robot relies on a static occupancy grid map, a localization algorithm, and a global planner to navigate autonomously.

A. Collision Probability Risk Maps

Obstacles’ position, dimensions, velocities, and the associated covariance matrices are estimated by a detection module. This module is composed of a clustering and a tracking phase, using a Kalman filter and a Global Nearest Neighbor algorithm for data association. From these quantities, we compute a collision probability map. Each cell is associated with the probability of having a collision between the robot and the obstacles when the robot center is located in that cell. To compute the map, the robot is approximated as a circle, and we assume Gaussian uncertainty on the obstacles position measurements. This approach allows us to treat the robot as a point-like entity during the path-planning phase.

B. Risk-Aware Planner

Our objective is to assess and modify a precomputed path from a global planner to obtain the path with the minimum risk. First, the reference path provided by the global planner is assessed. If the risk along the path exceeds a fixed threshold,

the Risk-Aware local planner is invoked, and a new safe trajectory is computed. We limit our planning to a local map centered around the robot, with dimensions of $8 \text{ m} \times 8 \text{ m}$. If the goal falls outside this local map, we select a local goal as the last waypoint within the local map. If this waypoint is not in a safe cell, we choose the closest safe cell as the local goal.

For an online implementation, we have used the Anytime Weighted A* algorithm, as presented in [5]. This algorithm operates similarly to A* but inserts a weight w in the evaluation function used for selecting the next node to expand the graph. This weight parameter allows us to strike a balance between performance in finding a solution and speed in searching new nodes. Once the first solution is found, the Anytime Weighted A* algorithm continues exploring open nodes until the specified time limit for the anytime problem is reached. The modified cost function for the A* problem would consider the distance, the probability of collision of each traversed cell (modified to allow A* additivity while preserving the same minimum for the global path), and the potential severity of the collision.

The collision's severity depends on the mobile base velocity, and the robot weight (considering also the load at that moment) [4]. In this work, we consider severity to be directly proportional to velocity as

$$\text{sev}_{\text{coll}} = \alpha \cdot \tilde{V}_{\mathcal{R}}, \quad (1)$$

where α is a parameter related to the robot's effective mass.

We approximate the velocity (and severity) to be constant for each iteration. This is reasonable as the planner runs at 10 Hz, being able to adjust the path in real time according to robot and obstacle velocity changes. The costs will be updated whenever the planner is invoked.

The vehicle is then steered along the obtained risk-aware path if the total risk is below a given threshold. If this is not the case due to the probability of collision which is too high, an active sensing module is activated for maximizing the information gathered by sensors. This is equivalent to minimizing the uncertainty and hence the probability of collision. To quantify the amount of information, we consider as a metric a suitable combination of the Constructability and Reachability Gramian, as described in [7].

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

We validate our approach using the omnidirectional Robotnik XL-Steel mobile base, equipped with two SICK s300 lidars,¹. The platform executes the risk-planner algorithm's path in omnidirectional mode using a PID controller. The proposed approach has been tested through simulation using RViz and Gazebo.

The risk-aware planner takes as input a reference trajectory (shown in green in figure 1) provided by a global planner. If the risk along the path exceeds a given threshold, the planner performs local modification of the current trajectory (shown

¹Robotnik xl-steel simulator, https://github.com/RobotnikAutomation/summit_xl_sim

Fig. 1: Paths generated with different robot velocities: **(a)** When the robot velocity is 0.1 m/s, the severity is small, and the robot passes between the two humans, even if the collision probability risk is not zero. **(b)** When the robot velocity is 0.5 m/s, the severity increases, and the minimal risk cost path is the one with zero risk collision probability.

in yellow in figure 1).

Figure 1 illustrates the distinct behaviours resulting from the severity component.

IV. FUTURE WORKS

In this paper, we have presented a framework to deal with collision risk in mobile robot navigation. Future works will be dedicated to including other risk factors such as e.g., battery discharge considering as probability a function of path length, friction coefficient, acceleration, and as severity the current state of charge of the battery. Moreover, by directly controlling the robot's velocity, we will study the best trade-off between slowing down and avoiding the obstacles by increasing the path length.

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